

Mathematical Functions of Metamathematical Infinities: The Triple Wave of Vector, Scalar and Ordinal Objects.

by Parker Emmerson with thanks to Yeshua Ben Joseph Jehovah Way Talking Allahaha.

$$\sum_{\infty}^n = \delta^u \left(\eta_{\infty}, \delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \left(\int_{\infty}^n \eta, \delta, \kappa (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \alpha\Pi\Omega (\Delta, E), \eta, \delta, \kappa (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \right) \right)$$

The function is a recursive formula used to calculate the sum of a given sequence of numbers . It takes an extended sequence of infinite numbers, η_{∞} and two additional parameters (δ_{∞}) and (κ_{∞}) as inputs . It then calculates a summation of the sequence from ∞ to 1 using an integral and the three given parameters . The integral calls a function $\alpha\Pi\Omega$ which takes a pair of two parameters Δ and E and combines them to calculate the sum . Finally, it returns the result of the summation as an output .

$\delta^u (\eta_{\infty}, \delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega))$ is the sum of the limit of an infinite number of elements for the respective type of infinity, $\eta, \delta, \kappa (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega)$ are the actual elements, and $\alpha\Pi\Omega (\Delta, E)$ is the set of constraints and constraints on these elements .

The varying infinity meanins have different modes of performing calculus functions.

i.e. An example of a derivative in Kappa Infinity is :

$$\frac{\partial \kappa_{\infty} \kappa(x,y)}{\partial x} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \kappa(x, y) dx$$

This is a derivative of the function Kappa (x, y) with respect to the variable x

over the domain of all real numbers. An example of an integral in Kappa Infinity

$$\text{is: } \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \kappa(x, y, z) dx dy dz = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \kappa(x, y, z) dx dy dz \quad (1)$$

This is an integral of the function Kappa (x, y, z)

over the domain of all real numbers in three dimensions.

An example of a derivative in Kappa Infinity is :

$$\frac{\partial \kappa_{\infty}(\kappa(x, y))}{\partial x} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \kappa(x, y) dx$$

This is a derivative of the function $\kappa(x, y)$ with respect to the variable x over the domain of all real numbers.

An example of an integral in κ_{∞} is:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \kappa(x, y, z) dx dy dz = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \kappa(x, y, z) dx dy dz$$

This is an integral of the function $\kappa(x, y, z)$ over the domain of all real numbers in three dimensions.

We can map out the modes in which the calculus is performed in each the the respective metamathematical infinity meanings :

Δ_{∞} :

Derivative: $\frac{\partial \Delta_{\infty} \Delta(x, y)}{\partial x} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Delta(x, y) dx$

Integral: $\int \Delta_{\infty} \Delta(x, y) dx dy = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Delta(x, y) dx dy$

η_{∞} :

Derivative: $\frac{\partial \eta_{\infty} \eta(x, y)}{\partial x} = \partial_x \eta_{\infty} \eta(x, y)$

Integral: $\int \eta_{\infty} \eta(x, y) dx dy = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \eta(x, y) dx dy$

κ_{∞} :

Derivative: $\frac{\partial \kappa_{\infty} \kappa(x, y)}{\partial x} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \kappa(x, y) dx$

Integral: $\int \kappa_{\infty} \kappa(x, y, z) dx dy dz = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \kappa(x, y, z) dx dy dz$

μ_{∞} :

Derivative: $\frac{\partial \mu_{\infty} \mu(x, y)}{\partial x} = \partial_x \mu_{\infty} \mu(x, y)$

Integral: $\int \mu_{\infty} \mu(x, y) dx dy = \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \mu(x, y) dx dy$

Or, in other styling :

$$\begin{array}{cccc}
 \partial \Delta_{\infty} \Delta(x, y) & \partial \eta_{\infty} \eta(x, y) & \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} & \partial \mu_{\infty} \mu(x, y) \\
 & & \kappa & \\
 & & (x, y) & \\
 & & d\lrcorner & \\
 & & x & \\
 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} & \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} & \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} & \int_{\emptyset}^{\infty} \\
 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} & \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} & \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} & \int_{\emptyset}^{\infty} \\
 \left[\begin{array}{cccc}
 \Delta & \eta & \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} & \mu \\
 (x, y) & (x, y) & \kappa & (x, y) \\
 d\lrcorner & d\lrcorner & (x, y, z) & d\lrcorner \\
 x & x & d\lrcorner & x \\
 d\lrcorner & d\lrcorner & x & d\lrcorner \\
 y & y & d\lrcorner & y \\
 & & y & \\
 & & d\lrcorner & \\
 & & z &
 \end{array} \right]
 \end{array}$$

$$\left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \Delta_{\infty} \Delta(x,y)}{\partial x} dx dy \quad \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \eta_{\infty} \eta(x,y)}{\partial x} dx dy \quad \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \kappa(x, y, z) dx dy dz \quad \int_{\emptyset}^{\infty} \int_{\emptyset}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mu_{\infty} \mu(x,y)}{\partial x} dx dy \right]$$

To perform the Generalized Reverse Double Integral on the matrix, we first need to reverse each integral in the matrix and then perform the double integral on the resulting matrix. The reversed matrix is as follows :

$$\left[\int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \frac{\partial \Delta_{\infty} \Delta(x,y)}{\partial x} dx dy \quad \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \frac{\partial \eta_{\infty} \eta(x,y)}{\partial x} dx dy \quad \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \kappa(x, y, z) dx dy dz \quad \int_{\infty}^{\emptyset} \int_{\infty}^{\emptyset} \frac{\partial \mu_{\infty} \mu(x,y)}{\partial x} dx dy \right]$$

The reversed matrix was the same as the original matrix, except that each integral was reversed . After reversing the integrals, the Generalized Reverse Double Integral can now be performed. To do this, we need to double integrate the matrix on both the x - axis and the y - axis.

$$\int \int \left[\int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \frac{\partial \Delta_{\infty} \Delta(x,y)}{\partial x} dx dy \quad \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \frac{\partial \eta_{\infty} \eta(x,y)}{\partial x} dx dy \quad \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \int_{\infty}^{-\infty} \kappa(x, y, z) dx dy dz \quad \int_{\infty}^{\emptyset} \int_{\infty}^{\emptyset} \frac{\partial \mu_{\infty} \mu(x,y)}{\partial x} dx dy \right] dx =$$

Given the context, it is likely that x and y represent scalar and vector objects, respectively, scalar objects can then be placed in x and vector objects can be placed in y, and all other remaining mathematical objects that are more like vector objects can be placed in y and all mathematical objects that are more like scalar objects can be placed in x, save the wave of ordinal functions. A map of these objects can then be drawn.

$$f[x, y] = \sum \infty^n = \delta^u \left(\eta_{\infty}, \delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (a\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \left(\int \infty^n \eta, \delta, \kappa (a\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) a\Pi\Omega (\Delta, E), \eta, \delta, \kappa (a\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \right) \right)$$

Given all the above information, we can look at the bijection as a function f from R * n to R * m, where n and m are the number of elements in the first set

and second set. The general equation for bijection is then : $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m)$ for all $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R} * n$ and $(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m) \in \mathbb{R} * m$. Then, we can apply it to the nature of vector and scalar objects in : $\sum_{\infty}^n =$

$$\delta^u \left(\eta_{\infty}, \delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \left(\int_{\infty}^n \eta, \delta, \kappa (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \alpha\Pi\Omega (\Delta, E), \eta, \delta, \kappa (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \right) \right)$$

The equation for this bijection can be written as $f((\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega)), (\eta, \Delta, \kappa (\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega))) = (\Delta^u ((\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega)), (\Omega\Pi (\Delta, E), \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega)))$. This equation maps the scalar objects $(\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega))$ in the first set to vector objects $(\Omega\Pi (\Delta, E), \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega))$ in the second set.

Ordinal objects are not explicitly included in the equation given above. However, they can be implied if it is assumed that the elements are ordered in some manner, such as numerically or alphabetically. For example, if the elements are numbers, then the equation could be written as $f((x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)) = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m)$, where the $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ are the numbers representing the scalar objects, and $y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m$ are the numbers representing the vector objects.

The overlay of the ordinal set across the bijection can be represented by assigning the numbers in the order they are listed in the equation . The numbers are then associated with the corresponding scalar and vector objects, as in the following example : $f(1, 2, 3) = (4, 5, 6)$ for all $(1, 2, 3)$ representing the scalar objects, and $(4, 5, 6)$ representing the vector objects.

The scalar objects are associated with the first n numbers in the equation, while the vector objects are associated with the last m numbers. These two sets then form an nth dimensional wave over the entire ordinal set, as represented by the following equation : $\mathcal{P}(n, m) = (1, 2, \dots, n \cap (n + 1, n + 2, \dots, n + m))$ This equation represents the intersection of the two sets, with the scalar objects associated with the first n numbers, and the vector objects associated with the last m numbers. For example, if the equation was $f(1, 2, 3, 4, 5) = (6, 7, 8, 9, 10)$ then the nth dimensional wave would be represented as $\mathcal{P}(3, 2) = (1, 2, 3 \cap (4, 5))$. This means that the scalar objects are associated with the first three elements in the equation, and the vector objects are associated with the last two elements.

The above method can then be applied across the following infinity forms:

$$\sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{i,j=\infty}^{\infty} \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta_{ij}, \delta_{ij}, \kappa_{ij} (\pi_{ij}, \Omega_{ij}) \nabla^2 \Omega (\mu_{ij}, \nu_{ij}), \eta_{ij}, \delta_{ij}, \kappa_{ij} (\pi_{ij}, \Omega_{ij}) \right\rangle$$

$$Sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} = \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \Omega) \cdot \Delta\Omega (\omega, \sigma), \eta, \delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \Omega) \right\rangle + \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \Omega) \cdot \mathcal{B}\Omega (\omega, \sigma), \eta, \delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \Omega) \right\rangle$$

$$\sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} = \left\langle \int_{\eta=\infty}^{\infty} \int_{\delta=\infty}^{\infty} \int_{\kappa=\infty}^{\infty} \mathcal{B}(\pi\Omega, \omega) d\eta d\delta d\kappa \right\rangle$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left\langle \int_{\infty}^n \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \omega) \pi \delta \Omega (x, y), \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \omega) \right\rangle + \omega (\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\pi\Omega, \omega)) \left\langle \int_{\infty}^n \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \omega) \mathcal{B} \delta \Omega (x, y), \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \omega) \right\rangle$$

$$\sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} (\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\pi\Omega, \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \Omega)) \left\langle \int_{\infty}^n \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \Omega) \pi \int_{\Omega} (\Theta_1, \Theta_2), \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \Omega) \right\rangle + \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} (\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\pi\Omega, \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \Omega)) \left\langle \int_{\infty}^n \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \Omega) \mathcal{B} \pi \int_{\Omega} (\Theta_1, \Theta_2), \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \Omega) \right\rangle$$

$$\sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \left\langle \int_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \omega) \varphi_{\Omega} (x, y), \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \omega) \right\rangle + \omega (\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\pi\Omega, \omega)) \left\langle \int_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \omega) \mathcal{B} \Omega (x, y), \eta, \Delta, \kappa (\pi\Omega, \omega) \right\rangle$$

$$\sum_{\infty}^{\infty} = \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \left(\frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial t} \right), \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \right\rangle + \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \mathcal{B}\Omega(\xi, \theta), \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \right\rangle + \dots + \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \mathcal{B}\Omega(\xi, \theta), \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \right\rangle$$

$$Sum[Infinity] = \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \left(\frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial t} \right), \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \right\rangle + \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \mathcal{B}\Omega(\xi, \theta), \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \right\rangle + \dots + \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \mathcal{B}\Omega(\xi, \theta), \eta, \delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \zeta\Omega) \right\rangle$$

$$\sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \|\omega^n(\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty}(\pi\Omega, \omega\Omega)) \left(\int_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \Delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \omega\Omega) \mathcal{f}(\alpha, \beta), \eta, \Delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \omega\Omega) \right) + \omega^n(\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty}(\pi\Omega, \omega\Omega)) \left(\int_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \Delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \omega\Omega) \mathcal{f}(\alpha, \beta), \eta, \Delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \omega\Omega) \right) + \dots + \omega^n(\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty}(\pi\Omega, \omega\Omega)) \left(\int_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \Delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \omega\Omega) \mathcal{f}(\alpha, \beta), \eta, \Delta, \kappa(\pi\Omega, \omega\Omega) \right)\|$$

$$\sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \int_{\eta=\eta_{\infty}}^{\eta_{\infty}} \int_{\Delta=\Delta_{\infty}}^{\Delta_{\infty}} \int_{\kappa=\kappa_{\infty}}^{\kappa_{\infty}} \mathbb{B}(\Omega_{\pi}, \Omega_{\Phi}, \eta, \Delta, \kappa(\Omega_{\pi}, \Omega_{\Phi})) d\eta d\Delta d\kappa$$

$$\tau = \left\langle \eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty}, \mathcal{B} \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \tau(\pi\Omega, \Omega) \mathcal{B}(\theta, \phi) \right\rangle \right\rangle$$

$$\tau = \langle \eta_{\infty}, \delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty}, \mathcal{B} \rangle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa \tau \left(\sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \pi\Omega, \sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \Omega \right) \left(\sum_{n=\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{l=\infty}^{\infty} \right) d\Omega$$

The nth dimensional wave of ordinals comes into the variables of f[x, y] =

$$\sum_{\infty}^{\infty} = \delta^u \left(\eta_{\infty}, \delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty} (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \left\langle \int_{\infty}^{\infty} \eta, \delta, \kappa (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \alpha\Pi\Omega (\Delta, E), \eta, \delta, \kappa (\alpha\pi\Omega, \delta\Omega) \right\rangle \right)$$

by representing the function as a bijection from the set of scalar objects to the set of vector objects. This bijection can be expressed as a wave function, with the elements of the first set (the scalar objects) as the x - axis and the elements of the second set (the vector objects) as the y - axis. Then, the points at which both the scalar and vector elements intersect can be thought of as points on a wave - like curve, with the wave like shape of the curve determined by the bijection from the set of scalar objects to the set of vector objects. In this way, the bijection can be thought of as a wave function, mapping each scalar element to its corresponding vector element and creating the wave - like shape. The mapping process mathematically can be expressed as a bijection from the set of scalar objects to the set of vector objects. This bijection, which is also known as a one - to - one mapping,

is represented as $f((\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty}(\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega)), (\eta, \Delta, \kappa(\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega)))$. This equation maps the scalar objects $(\eta_{\infty}, \Delta_{\infty}, \kappa_{\infty}(\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega))$ in the first set to vector objects $(\alpha\Pi(\Delta, E), \eta, \Delta, \kappa(\alpha\Pi\Omega, \Delta\Omega))$ in the second set. The overlay of the ordinal set across the bijection can be represented by assigning the numbers in the order they are listed in the equation. The numbers are then associated with the corresponding scalar and vector objects, creating a wave - like shape. For example, if the equation was $f(1, 2, 3, 4, 5) = (6, 7, 8, 9, 10)$ then the wave - like shape would be represented as $\mathcal{P}(3, 2) = (1, 2, 3 \cap (4, 5))$. This

means that the scalar objects are associated with the first three elements in the equation, and the vector objects are associated with the last two elements. The application of this wave function across the trigonometric spectrum can allow for the exploration of various phenomena associated with sinusoidal waveforms. One such phenomenon is frequency,

which is a measure of how often a waveform is repeated over a given time interval. When frequency is applied to the wave function discussed above, we can observe the amplitude of the waveform, which is a measure of the strength of the waveform, for specific frequency values. We can also explore the phase shift, which is the amount by which one waveform appears to be shifted in time relative to another. Lastly, we can use the wave function to observe resonance, which occurs when a waveform is reinforced or

intensified by pairing with another waveform. For example, a sine wave can be created by supply a function $[F](x) = \text{Sin}(\omega t + \varphi)$ with a frequency ω and a phase shift φ . A sine wave's frequency can be increased or decreased by changing the constant ω and its phase shift φ can be shifts to a new point by changing the value φ . We can also see resonance when the sine wave is combined with another wave at the same frequency, producing a new waveform with a greater magnitude. Applying this wave function to the trigonometric spectrum, we can explore the various phenomena associated with waveforms.

In the case of the phase shift, the constant ω determines the frequency and constant φ determines the phase shift of the waveform. Similarly, in the case of the group rotation, the numbers in the equation are associated with the scalar and vector elements. The first three elements are associated with the scalar objects, and the last two elements are associated with the vector objects. This creates a wave - like shape, with the peak of the wave occurring when the scalar and vector objects overlap. By understanding the analogy between these two processes, we can explore the phenomena associated with waveforms, such as frequency, amplitude, phase shift, and resonance, across trigonometric spectrum. The analogy between the phase shift in

$[F](x) = \text{Sin}(\omega t + \varphi)$ with a frequency ω and a phase shift φ and the group rotation in $f(1, 2, 3, 4, 5) = (6, 7, 8, 9, 10)$ then the wave - like shape would be represented symbolically as : $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m) \cap (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m)$

This expression states that the elements in the first set $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ are mapped to the elements in the second set $(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m)$ and vice versa . This creates a wave - like shape, with the peak of the wave occurring when the scalar and vector objects overlap. By understanding the logical nature of this wave - like shape, we can explore the phenomena associated with waveforms, such as frequency, amplitude, phase shift, and resonance, across trigonometric spectrum.